

Ultrasound-Guided Pigtail Catheter Drainage for Liver Abscess: A Minimally Invasive Approach

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Abstract:

Background: Liver abscesses, caused by bacteria, amoebae, and fungi, can significantly impact health, particularly in tropical regions. Traditional management involved extensive surgeries, leading to high morbidity and long hospital stays. Recent advancements have shifted the focus to less invasive techniques like ultrasound-guided pigtail catheter drainage.

Methodology: This Prospective study, conducted over a year at Nalanda medical college and Hospital, included 60 adult patients with solitary liquefied liver abscesses. Comprehensive pre-intervention investigations were performed. Under local anesthesia, a 10 Fr pigtail catheter was inserted into the abscess cavity, guided by ultrasound. Post-procedure, patients were monitored and discharged after confirming no complications. Weekly follow-ups with USG and CBP continued until abscess resolution. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0.

Results: The study showed that 92% of patients experienced right upper quadrant pain, 83% had fever, and 88% had abscesses in the right lobe. Pus cultures revealed no growth in 70% of cases. The abscess cavity volumes ranged from 100 to 350 ml. Complications included pain at the catheter site (93%) and catheter blockage (18%). All patients had successful abscess resolution without requiring laparotomy.

Conclusion: Ultrasound-guided pigtail catheter drainage is an effective, safe, and minimally invasive method for managing solitary liver abscess, reducing the need for open surgery, hospital stay, costs, and complications. This technique offers a preferable alternative to traditional surgical approaches.

Keywords: pigtail catheter, Liver abscess, USG, Drainage.

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Introduction

A liver abscess refers to a collection of pus within the liver, typically caused by pyogenic bacteria, amoebae, and occasionally fungi. [1] These abscesses can be solitary or multiple and may affect the right lobe, left lobe, or both lobes of the liver. [2] While a liver abscess can be caused by a single organism, most cases are polymicrobial. [3]

The prognosis for patients with liver abscesses is influenced by the type of fluid within the cavity, as noted by Hippocrates. [4] Liver abscesses remain a significant cause of morbidity and mortality, particularly in tropical countries. [5] However, early diagnosis and treatment, facilitated by advances in diagnostic and therapeutic modalities, have improved patient outcomes. Historically, extensive surgeries were performed to manage these conditions, leading to increased morbidity, mortality, complications like adhesions, and longer hospital stays, which raised the risk of infections. Nowadays, percutaneous therapeutic procedures, such as pigtail catheter insertion, are increasingly

being used as alternatives to open surgical laparotomies. [6-8]

Traditionally, percutaneous needle aspiration was not widely adopted due to the difficulty in accurately locating collections. The advent of ultrasound has made percutaneous pigtail catheter drainage a safe, effective, and minimally invasive option that allows precise localization of the drainage site. While percutaneous drainage has been used for liver abscesses for over six decades, it initially had high failure rates due to poor localization. This study aims to demonstrate that ultrasound-guided pigtail catheter drainage can be a safe, effective, and precise method for managing liver abscess cavity collections.

Methods

This prospective study was conducted over a period of one year in Nalanda medical college and Hospital Patna. Patients with abnormal coagulation profiles were first stabilized before undergoing any

intervention. Comprehensive investigations, including USG/CECT abdomen, CBP, RBS, Blood Urea, Serum Creatinine, LFT, HIV, HBsAg, HCV, CT, BT, PT, APTT, INR, Blood grouping, and typing, were performed for all patients.

Initially, 60 patients received medical treatment with antibiotics and NSAIDs. Inclusion criteria included adults >18 years presenting with a solitary liquefied abscess cavity. Those with multiple liver abscesses were excluded from the study.

One unit of packed red blood cells was reserved for each patient. The procedure was conducted in the USG suite under strict antiseptic conditions, with local anesthesia (2% lignocaine) and USG guidance. A 10 Fr pigtail catheter was inserted into the abscess cavity using the Seldinger technique. The catheter was secured and connected to a urosac bag after confirming proper drainage of pus and the correct positioning of the catheter's tip. A 10 ml pus sample was sent for culture and sensitivity testing.

Post-procedure, patients received Inj. Tramadol 50 mg in 100 ml NS IV twice daily. There, PR, and BP were monitored hourly. An abdominal USG was performed on the same evening, and if there were no signs of free fluid in the peritoneal cavity, peritonitis, or respiratory distress, the patient was discharged.

The first follow-up occurred one week after catheter placement, involving an abdominal USG and CBP to check for a decrease in the size of the abscess cavity. Subsequent USGs and CBPs were performed weekly. Drains were removed once the

collapse of the abscess cavity was confirmed via USG. Informed written consent was obtained from all patients after explaining the potential complications of the procedure. Data collected during the study were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using version 25.0 of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Results

In this study, 60 patients underwent USG-guided pigtail catheter insertion for solitary liver abscess. The symptoms and signs observed included pain in the right upper quadrant (92%), fever (83%), generalized weakness (83%), chills and rigors (78%), hepatomegaly (50%), jaundice (42%), vomiting (37%), pallor (35%), anorexia (35%), weight loss (30%), pleural effusion (17%), and diarrhea (12%).

Laboratory investigations showed leucocytosis (90%), elevated total bilirubin (40%), and anemia (35%). The right lobe was most commonly involved (88%), followed by the left lobe (12%). Microorganisms isolated from pus after 48 hours of aerobic culture showed no growth in 70% of cases, *E. coli* in 15%, *S. aureus* in 8%, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in 7%.

The volume of the abscess cavity varied, with 100-150 ml in 35%, 151-200 ml in 30%, 201-250 ml in 20%, 251-300 ml in 10%, and 301-350 ml in 5% of patients. Complications of the procedure included pain at the catheter site (93%), blockage of the catheter (18%), and displacement of the catheter tip (7%).

Table 1: Symptoms and Signs in study participants

Symptom/Sign	N	Percentage (%)
Pain in right upper quadrant	55	91.7%
Fever	50	83.3%
Generalized weakness	50	83.3%
Chills and rigors	47	78.3%
Hepatomegaly	30	50.0%
Jaundice	25	41.7%
Vomiting	22	36.7%
Pallor	21	35.0%
Anorexia	21	35.0%
Weight loss	18	30.0%
Pleural effusion	10	16.7%
Diarrhea	7	11.7%

Table 2: Laboratory Investigations in study participants

Laboratory Finding	N	Percentage (%)
Leucocytosis	54	90.0%
Elevated total bilirubin	24	40.0%
Anemia	21	35.0%

Table 3: Microorganisms Isolated in Pus in study participants

Microorganism	N	Percentage (%)
No growth	42	70.0%
E. coli	9	15.0%
S. aureus	5	8.3%
Klebsiella pneumoniae	4	6.7%

Tab 4: Volume of abscess cavity in study subjects

Volume of abscess cavity	No	%
100-150 ml	21	35
151-200 ml	18	30
201-250 ml	12	20
251-300 ml	6	10
301-350 ml	3	5

Table 5: Complications of the Procedure in study participants

Complication	N	Percentage (%)
Pain at catheter site	56	93.3%
Blockage of the catheter	11	18.3%
Displacement of catheter tip	4	6.7%

Discussion

This prospective study utilized ultrasound-guided pigtail catheter insertion for assessing and draining intra-hepatic collections or abscesses. The approach has significantly enhanced treatment outcomes, notably reducing both mortality and morbidity rates. This improvement is attributed to the combined administration of antibiotics and precise imaging guidance, which have largely replaced the need for traditional open surgical drainage.

Percutaneous drainage, whether through needle aspiration or a catheter, has become the established approach for managing liver abscesses. While needle aspiration can require repeated procedures, making it less advantageous, the use of a pigtail catheter is generally considered a superior treatment option. [9]

Liver abscess remains a significant health concern among the economically disadvantaged population in India, contributing substantially to morbidity and mortality. Various treatment options, such as percutaneous needle aspiration, percutaneous catheter drainage, or open drainage, are available for managing liver abscesses caused by different factors. [10]

Percutaneous drainage methods, including needle aspiration and catheter drainage, have largely replaced open surgical procedures due to their effectiveness. [11] Clinical studies, such as those by Beger et al, have shown improved outcomes following needle aspiration of abscess cavities. Surgical drainage remains reserved for cases where percutaneous methods are inadequate. [12]

Percutaneous drainage under ultrasound guidance is generally safe when performed by experienced practitioners, with minimal risks such as organ

perforation, bleeding, or infection. [13] It is now considered the preferred treatment for intra-abdominal collections and abscess cavities. This study included patients with various comorbidities, such as diabetes mellitus, acalculous cholecystitis, and obesity. [14] Our study specifically focused on the use of ultrasound-guided pigtail catheter insertion to drain solitary liquefied liver abscess cavity. Common complications included pain, catheter blockage, and catheter tip displacement, necessitating repositioning under ultrasound guidance and regular saline flushing to prevent blockage. Larger or thick pus-filled cavities required extended drainage periods, potentially mitigated by using wider bore catheters. [15,16]

Study limitations included a small patient sample and a lack of differentiation in the causes of liver abscesses. Nevertheless, our findings support the safety and efficacy of ultrasound-guided pigtail catheter placement for draining these abscesses, reducing hospital stays compared to open drainage procedures. Optimal catheter selection and patient suitability are crucial for successful abscess cavity drainage. Similar conclusions were drawn in related studies by Gupta et al and Malik et al regarding the drainage of liver abscesses. [17,18]

Conclusion

The study concluded that employing a precise technique for pigtail catheter insertion under ultrasound guidance allows for the effective management of most intra hepatic abscess without the need for exploratory laparotomy. This method significantly reduces costs, morbidity, complications, hospital stay duration, and the risk of hospital-acquired infections.

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